

ISic0492

Honours for Rubellinus

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

Object

statue base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

Seen by Metcalfe in 2018

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Mazara

Place of origin (modern)

Mazara del Vallo

Provenance

First recorded in the area of the Palazzo Vescovile, in the courtyard of which it is currently located

Coordinates

37.651862, 12.590205

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Mazara del Vallo, Palazzo Vescovile (courtyard)

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. M(arco) Rubellino
2. P(ubli) f(ilio) Publ(io) Cestiano Cras
3. siciano flam(ini) divor(um) Augg(ustorum)
4. perp(etuo) trib(un) [x[---] ap[--- --- --- --- ---] qv[---]]

Apparatus

Text of CIL, compared against photograph

Translation

Commentary

The upper part of the stone is currently located in the courtyard of the Palazzo Vescovile in Mazara del Vallo; there is no trace of the lower part of the stone, previously recorded in CIL and by earlier authors. The text almost certainly honours the same individual as ISic3460 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/>

inscription/ISic3460] , found in Marsala in 2010. Whether the stone was transferred after antiquity from Marsala, as has often been suggested, or whether Mazara was a subordinate community of Lilybaeum in the Roman period, remains uncertain.

Digital identifiers:

TM 491718

EDCS 22000798

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum.* Berlin. At 10.7212 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Silvestrini, Marina 2020. Un autorevole tribuno militare e una titolatura imperiale in due epigrafi inedite di Lilibeo. *Zeitschrift für Papyrologie und Epigraphik.* 213: 294-300. At 294, 296-298 with figs. 4-5

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Photo courtesy of M. Silvestrini